

Resource Allocation and Slicing Strategy for Multiple Services Co-Existence in Wireless Train Communication Network

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Abstract—Wireless train communication network (WLTCN) is an emerging technology for enabling intelligent rail vehicles. It is responsible for providing train control services (TCS), passenger information services (PIS), and train sensing services (TSS). These services within WLTCN have notably different quality of service (QoS) requirements from traditional telecommunication services. In this paper, to incorporate multiple services in a single WLTCN, we propose a radio access network (RAN) slicing architecture empowered WLTCN to satisfy the demands of services and save bandwidth resource. In particular, the service and slicing models of TCS, PIS, and TSS are investigated. By analyzing the heterogeneous characteristics and QoS requirements of the above services within WLTCN, we exploit the orthogonal multiple access scheme for TCS and PIS and the non-orthogonal multiple access scheme for TSS, respectively. The system bandwidth minimization problem is formulated with slicing resource allocation for TCS, PIS, and TSS and non-orthogonal access grouping for TSS terminals as a mixed-integer nonlinear programming (MINLP). To solve the intractable MINLP, the original problem is transformed and decoupled into the two subproblems. Then, we propose a joint bandwidth optimization and terminal clustering (JBOTC) algorithm to tackle the bandwidth allocation problem with optimal terminal grouping strategy for TSS effectively. The closed-form expressions of the optimal bandwidth allocation strategy for three services are derived. The simulation results illustrate the performance superiority for saving bandwidth of the JBOTC algorithm to the benchmark schemes. Our proposed slicing strategy enables WLTCN to support heterogeneous services co-existence with minimal bandwidth consumption.

Index Terms—Wireless train communication network, network slicing, resource allocation, joint unicast and multicast

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I. INTRODUCTION

THE train communication network (TCN) serves as a central hub for data exchange throughout the rail vehicles. It plays a crucial role in ensuring the safe operations of trains while also improving operational speed and level of intelligence. Unlike the 5G for Railways (5G-R) system, which focuses on train-to-ground communication and infrastructure monitoring, the TCN is tailored for data communications among onboard subsystems and devices of the train. It covers scenarios such as intra-vehicle, intra-consist, inter-consist, and train-to-train communications [2]. The traditional TCN relies solely on the wired bus or switch network technologies [3], which hinders the trains from flexibly upgrading and carrying intelligent services, and restricts the advancement of train intelligence level [4]. To address the limitations of traditional TCN, the wireless train communication network (WLTCN) is the object of great attention due to its high flexibility and cost-effectiveness for providing comprehensive multiple services in a single network. The Roll2Rail project supported by the European Commission has developed a new WLTCN to eliminate the need for cables and simplify the coupling procedure of trains, which significantly reduces life-cycle costs [5].

Based on the different characteristics of services, the services in WLTCN are classified neatly into three categories with distinct quality of service (QoS) requirements: train control services (TCS), passenger information services (PIS), and train sensing services (TSS). Mainly, due to the high relevance with the operation of trains, TCS have strict requirements in latency, jitter, and reliability [6]. In contrast, PIS mainly include multimedia services. Due to the enormous amount of video streaming traffic, PIS require a high transmission rate. TSS carry the train condition monitoring and perception data. Taking into account the high demands of state monitoring and perception in WLTCN, it is essential to support connecting numerous terminals adequately [7], [8]. To fulfill the different QoS requirements of TCS, PIS, and TSS, three individual networks are deployed for each type of service in the rail vehicles [2].

Instead, the solution to integrate heterogeneous services into a single WLTCN can increase flexibility and reduce the costs of the network [9]. The available wireless technologies for WLTCN are summarized [10], which are mainly responsible for the information interaction of coupled trains. However,

they cannot enable the WLTCN to provide multiple services with different QoS requirements. Thus, it is essential to realize the co-existence and transmission of heterogeneous services within a WLTCN by using suitable wireless solutions. Due to the high throughput, ultra-reliable and low-latency, and massive connection capabilities [11]–[13], the fifth generation (5G) technology with slicing technology is an effective method to enable the WLTCN to incorporate heterogeneous services.

In the existing works, integrated slicing technology and novel network architectures for services co-existence have attracted a lot of attention. Specifically, by investigating the multi-dimensional resources and network functions at the edge of radio access network (RAN) provided by mobile edge computing (MEC), the system can satisfy the demands of services [14], [15]. In a hybrid cloud architecture, the network slicing deployment and resource allocation have been studied with the requirements of 5G services and the characteristics of cloud architecture [16]. Moreover, considering the slicing and resource allocation for 5G services, the service multiplexing strategies for enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB) and ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC) have been proposed [17]–[19]. Some slicing schemes can also ensure the performance of eMBB, URLLC, and massive machine type communication (mMTC) services [20], [21].

However, the slicing strategies mentioned above mainly focus on the slicing architecture designs and resource allocation problems for traditional services of telecommunication, such as eMBB, URLLC, and mMTC, which are not suitable for the WLTCN due to the following reasons:

- 1) The characteristics and QoS requirements of services within WLTCN are different from the services of telecommunication operators:
 - TCS should be considered with terminal-to-terminal QoS requirements instead of end-to-end ones, which are distinguished from the services of telecommunication operators. Considering the real-time characteristic, TCS have strict latency and jitter requirements on terminal-to-terminal transmission.
 - The WLTCN provides multiple services with various QoS requirements. However, most previous works have focused on slicing framework and resource allocation for one or two types of services, such as eMBB with URLLC, and URLLC with mMTC. The suitable slicing strategy for WLTCN needs to be explored.
 - The WLTCN has hybrid unicast and multicast transmission demands for services. TCS rely on unicast and multiple multicast group transmission modes for uplink and downlink, respectively. PIS are downlink services that use a single multicast group transmission mode. TSS are uplink services with unicast mode.
- 2) The design objective of the WLTCN is to save bandwidth resource, which is distinct from the literature. The WLTCN is a private network. However, there is currently no licensed spectrum specially allocated for WLTCN. To deploy WLTCN, spectrum is obtained by leasing it from telecommunication operators [7]. Saving bandwidth resource can reduce the spectrum trading costs

and support more smart services in the future.

In this paper, we propose a RAN slicing architecture within WLTCN to realize the multiple services co-existence, including TCS, PIS, and TSS. We investigate the service and slice models, hybrid multiple access schemes, and heterogeneous QoS requirements guarantee for the above services. Then, the system bandwidth minimization problem is formulated with bandwidth allocation for TCS, PIS, and TSS and non-orthogonal access grouping for TSS terminals. We propose a feasible algorithm to solve the bandwidth allocation problem and derive the optimal slicing strategy in WLTCN. The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows.

- We build up the RAN slicing architecture within WLTCN to provide TCS, PIS, and TSS jointly. The service and slicing models of the above services are investigated. Then, based on the heterogeneous characteristics and QoS requirements of services, we exploit the orthogonal multiple access scheme for TCS and PIS and the non-orthogonal multiple access scheme for TSS, respectively.
- The system bandwidth minimization problem is formulated with slicing resource allocation for TCS, PIS, and TSS and non-orthogonal access grouping for TSS terminals as a mixed-integer nonlinear programming (MINLP). Hence, we decompose the original problem into two subproblems to tackle the intractable MINLP.
- We propose a joint bandwidth optimization and terminal clustering (JBOTC) algorithm to search for the optimal slicing resource allocation of TCS, PIS, and TSS and the terminal grouping strategy of TSS. The closed-form expressions of the optimal bandwidth allocation for three services are derived based on dual decomposition theory. Additionally, We demonstrate the complexity of the algorithm, and the simulation results show that the proposed JBOTC algorithm outperforms the baseline schemes.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. The related works are introduced in Section II. In Section III, the RAN slicing framework within WLTCN is proposed. Besides, the service and slicing models, and multiple access schemes are investigated for TCS, PIS, and TSS. In Section IV, we analyze the QoS requirements of the three services in WLTCN. Then, we formulate the slicing strategy as the system bandwidth minimization problem in Section V. In Section VI, the closed-form expressions of the optimal bandwidth allocation of three services are derived, and a JBOTC algorithm is proposed for the joint bandwidth allocation and terminal grouping strategy. Moreover, we present our simulation results in Section VII, followed by the conclusions in Section VIII.

II. RELATED WORK

In this section, we discuss the related research works on the network slicing architecture design. Besides, we also introduce the works on slicing resource allocation problem for multiple services.

A. Network Slicing Architecture Design

At present, notable research efforts have endeavored to propose various innovative approaches about slicing architectures

design [14]–[16], [22]–[24]. Wang *et al.* [14] have investigated joint optimization of communication, computing, and caching resources in multi-access edge network slicing architecture using a novel deep reinforcement learning approach. Ye *et al.* [15] have introduced a hierarchical network slicing architecture based on non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) in the novel 6G full-spectrum scalable cell-free radio access network with MEC. Considering a hybrid cloud infrastructure, a joint optimal deployment of virtual network functions and allocation of computational resource has been researched [16]. Tang *et al.* [22] have proposed a digital twin (DT) network-assisted industry internet of things network slicing architecture and a distributed algorithm aimed at maximizing the equilibrium rate weighted net profit of network providers. To enable and exploit statistical multiplexing, Chatterjee *et al.* [23] have proposed an optimization framework for orchestrating virtualized cellular networks with two phases: virtual network deployment and statistical multiplexing. Liu *et al.* have proposed an intelligent resource integration architecture named Slicing4Meta to provide VR/AR immersive services and digital twin services [24]. In addition, telecommunication operators have gained valuable empirical experience in network architecture within the rail transportation industry. For example, China Telecom and ZTE have built a complete 5G indoor system inside the metro carriages, utilizing the industry-first two-level architecture of ZTE to develop smart metro applications for passengers [25]. However, the above network architectures are proposed to support the 5G services. The different characteristics of RAN slicing architecture within WLTCN remain to be explored.

B. Slicing and Resource Allocation for Multiple Services

For slicing and resource allocation for multiple services with different QoS requirements [17]–[21], [26]–[32], within the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) standard, two potential approaches for multiplexing eMBB and URLLC services have been defined: preemptive (puncturing) scheduling and orthogonal scheduling [17]. A resource scheduling problem based on preemptive and Lyapunov optimization schemes has been investigated to support service multiplexing for eMBB and URLLC users [18]. Tang *et al.* [19] have reserved the bandwidth resource for multicast eMBB and unicast URLLC slice requests to maximize the revenue of operators. Manzoor *et al.* [26] have introduced a contract theory framework to allow URLLC users to choose between puncturing or superposition approaches dynamically. Additionally, Yin *et al.* [27] have jointly utilized network slicing to incorporate different types of services and enhance the connection density with NOMA technology. Yang *et al.* [28] have investigated the problem of slicing a RAN enabling coordinated multi-point (CoMP) transmissions for multiplexing multicast eMBB and bursty URLLC services to maximize slice utilities. For the eMBB and URLLC users in 5G downlink transmission, resource allocation solutions based on the convex relaxation and greedy algorithm have been proposed to maximize eMBB utility under URLLC constraints [29]. RAN slicing strategy for massive internet of things (mIoT) and bursty URLLC service multiplexing has also received attention [30]. Popovski

Fig. 1: Illustration of the RAN slicing framework empowered WLTCN.

et al. [20] have focused on exploring the potential benefits of non-orthogonal sharing of RAN resource in uplink communications for eMBB, mMTC, and URLLC devices, considering heterogeneous non-orthogonal multiple access (H-NOMA) and orthogonal multiple access (H-OMA) schemes. Liu *et al.* [21] have analyzed the performance of different slicing schemes in the uplink and proposed a slicing scheme based on rate-splitting multiple access (RSMA) to ensure the performance of eMBB, URLLC, and mMTC services. Furthermore, deep reinforcement learning frameworks have been utilized to schedule resource with puncture structures for eMBB and URLLC users [31], [32].

In the above-mentioned research, slicing and resource allocation problems based on the QoS requirements of services within WLTCN have not been considered. In this work, we investigate a RAN slicing architecture to realize multiple services co-existence in WLTCN. Besides, slicing strategy and resource allocation for TCS, PIS, and TSS within WLTCN are considered.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

In this section, we illustrate the RAN slicing framework empowered WLTCN. The service and slicing models are employed for the diverse services, including TCS, PIS, and TSS. Besides, investigating the characteristics of the above services, we explore the hybrid multiple access schemes.

A. System Architecture and Service Models

As shown in Fig. 1, we consider a RAN slicing framework empowered WLTCN in a single carriage, where a base station (BS) communicates with multiple onboard terminals via an orthogonal slicing scheme. There are three types of terminals providing TCS, PIS, and TSS, which are wirelessly accessed to the 5G BS and fixed inside the train. We consider four types of service requests: uplink TCS (TCS^u), uplink TSS, downlink TCS (TCS^m), and downlink PIS, each represented by distinct data flows. To support the above service requests, the slicing resource is divided into four types of logically

separate network slices. Within each type, terminals are further divided into multiple slices based on QoS requirements. The BS is equipped with K antennas, while each terminal has a single antenna.

The WLTCN provides TCS, PIS, and TSS. TCS are used for information exchange between the onboard subsystems. Each onboard subsystem, such as the center control unit (CCU), brake control unit (BCU), and traction control unit (TCU), consists of a communication terminal and mechanical part. The data of TCS are transmitted from terminal to terminal with hybrid unicast and multicast modes. The reason is that the status of each subsystem should be shared with multiple related subsystems for train operation. For example, we consider that the data flow TCU sends its status information to BCU and CCU. TCU sends its data to the core network in unicast mode on the uplink, and then the data are transmitted to BCU and CCU in multicast mode on the downlink. The characteristic of TCS is real-time with strict latency and jitter requirements.

PIS are used for passenger information transmission, such as safety tip video. The PIS flow uses multicast on the downlink, meaning that the safety tip video is sent to different terminals. Thus, PIS require a high transmission rate.

TSS are employed for the transmission of environment perception and train equipment condition monitoring information, such as the axle temperature, acceleration, noise in the carriage, and vibration data of the train bogie. The TSS flow uses unicast on the uplink. For instance, the axle temperature terminal uploads the collected information. TSS are characterized by an enormous number of terminals and limited device access probability.

B. Multiple Access

To meet the transmission demands in WLTCN, we propose hybrid access schemes for terminals carrying TCS, PIS, and TSS with orthogonal multiple access (OMA) and NOMA technology. On the one hand, to eliminate inter-slice interference, we exploit the OMA scheme to divide all slices including TCS, PIS, and TSS. Then, within a single slice, considering the different characteristics and QoS requirements of the above services, we exploit the OMA scheme for TCS and PIS and the NOMA scheme for TSS, respectively.

The OMA scheme is employed to mitigate inter-slice interference for three types of services to effectively guarantee the QoS requirements within WLTCN. Additionally, for TCS and PIS, OMA scheme is also utilized to eliminate intra-slice interference within a slice, which satisfies the data transmission requirements of TCS and PIS. However, for TSS, considering the massive access transmission demand, compared to the OMA, the NOMA scheme can significantly improve the connection number of the TSS terminals to guarantee the QoS requirement [33]. Therefore, we employ the NOMA scheme within the TSS slices and utilize successive interference cancellation (SIC) technology to eliminate inter-terminal interference. By employing the hybrid OMA and NOMA schemes, we can effectively provide TCS, PIS, and TSS with distinct QoS requirements in WLTCN.

C. Slicing Model

In this work, we consider that the whole system bandwidth resource can be divided into four types of logically separate network slices: unicast TCS slices (TCS^u), multicast TCS slices (TCS^m), PIS slices, and TSS slices.

TCS^u slices carry unicast train control traffic, and the slice set can be given as $\mathcal{S}^u = \{1, \dots, S^u\}$. TCS^m slices carry multicast train control traffic, which are denoted by a set $\mathcal{S}^m = \{1, \dots, S^m\}$. PIS slices are denoted by $\mathcal{S}^p = \{1, \dots, S^p\}$. TSS slices can be represented as $\mathcal{S}^o = \{1, \dots, S^o\}$. Let $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}^u \cup \mathcal{S}^m \cup \mathcal{S}^p \cup \mathcal{S}^o$. We divide the terminals with the same demands and QoS requirements into a slice. The number of terminals on the TCS^u slice $s \in \mathcal{S}^u$ is I_s^u , and the set of terminals can be given as $\mathcal{I}_s^u = \{1, \dots, I_s^u\}$. The number of terminals on the TCS^m slice $s \in \mathcal{S}^m$ is denoted by I_s^m , and the set of terminals is $\mathcal{I}_s^m = \{1, \dots, I_s^m\}$. The number of terminals on the PIS slice $s \in \mathcal{S}^p$ is I_s^p , and the set of terminals can be given as $\mathcal{I}_s^p = \{1, \dots, I_s^p\}$. Similarly, we have the number I_s^o and set $\mathcal{I}_s^o = \{1, \dots, I_s^o\}$ of terminals on the TSS slice $s \in \mathcal{S}^o$.

According to the multiple access schemes, the different types of slices are isolated by the OMA scheme, and the bandwidth resource can be reserved for slices in advance.

D. Signal Model

In the static train carriage, we assume that the perfect channel state information (CSI) between the BS and terminals can be estimated and channels are block-fading [34], [35]. $\mathbf{h}_i^d \in \mathcal{C}^K$ denotes the downlink channel vector from BS to terminal i . $\mathbf{h}_i^u \in \mathcal{C}^{1 \times K}$ is the uplink channel vector from terminal i to BS. All coefficients of channels are independent and identically distributed (i.i.d) complex Gaussian random variables with $\mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$. The received signal of terminal i in the downlink data transmission, i.e., multicast mode, is given by

$$y_i^d = \sqrt{P_i^{BS}} (\mathbf{h}_i^d)^H \mathbf{x}_i^d + \mathbf{n}_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_s^m \cup \mathcal{I}_s^p, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{n}_i is the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with zero mean and variation σ^2 of terminal i . We employ $(\cdot)^H$ to denote conjugate transpose, and Euclidean norm is denoted by $\|\cdot\|^2$. The transmitted signal from BS is $\mathbf{x}_i^d \in \mathcal{C}^K$ with $\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{x}_i^d\|^2] = 1$. P_i^{BS} denotes the transmit power of BS to the terminal i . Without taking into account interference, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of terminal $i \in \mathcal{I}_s^m \cup \mathcal{I}_s^p$ can be given as $\gamma_i^d = \frac{P_i^{BS} |(\mathbf{h}_i^d)^H \mathbf{x}_i^d|^2}{\sigma^2}$.

For the uplink data transmission, i.e., unicast mode, the received signal of terminal i is given by

$$y_i^u = \sqrt{P_i^t} \mathbf{h}_i^u \mathbf{x}_i^u + \mathbf{n}_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_s^u \cup \mathcal{I}_s^o, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_i^u \in \mathcal{C}^K$ is the transmitted signal from the terminal i with $\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{x}_i^u\|^2] = 1$. P_i^t denotes the transmit power of the terminal i . For the TCS^u slice s , the SNR of terminal $i \in \mathcal{I}_s^u$ is given by $\gamma_i^u = \frac{P_i^t |\mathbf{h}_i^u \mathbf{x}_i^u|^2}{\sigma^2}$. For the TSS slice s , it becomes possible to serve multiple terminals simultaneously in a shared frequency resource block due to the utilization of NOMA technology, and also introduces inter-terminal interference.

Hence, we consider the instantaneous signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) for terminal $i \in \mathcal{I}_s^o$ which is expressed detailedly in Section IV.

IV. QoS REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS WITHIN WLTCN

In this section, considering the heterogeneous characteristics of TCS, PIS, and TSS, we analyze the QoS requirements of services within WLTCN and use two critical attributes to represent each network slice.

Studying that TCS are related to the control and operation of trains, the QoS indicators of the TCS^u slice $s \in \mathcal{S}^u$ and TCS^m slice $s \in \mathcal{S}^m$ are maximum transmission delay, which are denoted as D_s^u and D_s^m , respectively. In terms of the PIS slice $s \in \mathcal{S}^p$, because of the enormous amount of video streaming traffic, we choose the minimum throughput as the QoS indicator, which is given by A_s^p . With the NOMA scheme exploited to TSS terminals, the BS can successfully decode packets satisfying the minimum transmission rate. Hence, we use the transmission rate threshold as the QoS indicator for TSS slice $s \in \mathcal{S}^o$, which is denoted as R_s^o . Furthermore, considering the possible network congestion caused by frequent access from the numerous TSS terminals, we define an access control mechanism to ensure a successful terminal access probability.

Therefore, associating with the slicing models in Section III, we denote each slice with an array containing two attributes, TCS^u slice s , TCS^m slice s , PIS slice s , and TSS slice s are represented by $\{I_s^u, D_s^u\}$, $\{I_s^m, D_s^m\}$, $\{I_s^p, A_s^p\}$, and $\{I_s^o, R_s^o\}$, respectively.

A. TCS^u Slices

We consider the short packet length for TCS slices. The finite block-length channel coding regime is used to characterize the achievable rate for TCS data [36]. The bandwidth of TCS^u slice s is $b_s^u = \sum_{i=1}^{I_s^u} b_{i,s}^u$, where $b_{i,s}^u$ is the bandwidth resource of terminal i on the slice s . With the short packet length of data, the spectrum efficiency (SE) $r_{i,s}^u$ of terminal i on the slice $s \in \mathcal{S}^u$ can be expressed as

$$r_{i,s}^u = \log(1 + \gamma_i^u) - \sqrt{\frac{C_i^u}{n_i}} Q^{-1}(\vartheta) \log e, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_s^u, \quad (3)$$

where $C_i^u = 1 - \frac{1}{(1 + \gamma_i^u)^2}$ represents the characteristic of channel, i.e., channel dispersion. $Q^{-1}(\cdot)$ denotes the inverse of the Gaussian Q-function, $\vartheta > 0$ is the transmission error probability, and n_i is the finite block-length. Hence, the delay constraint is

$$\max_{i \in \mathcal{I}_s^u} \left\{ \frac{F_{i,s}^u}{r_{i,s}^u b_{i,s}^u} \right\} \leq D_s^u, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^u, \quad (4)$$

where $F_{i,s}^u$ is the packet length of terminal i on the TCS^u slice s . Moreover, because the train operation information from each subsystem should be shared with other related subsystems simultaneously, TCS also have strict jitter requirements. Moreover, because the train operation information from each subsystem should be shared with other related subsystems simultaneously, TCS also have strict jitter requirements. Under deterministic transmission, the jitter distribution is symmetric around a mean value with no long tails. Hence, to support

deterministic transmission for TCS, we design the jitter as the difference between the packet transmission delay and the mean delay specifically for TCS terminals [37]. Let the transmission latency of terminal i on the TCS^u slice s be denoted as $T_{i,s}^u = \frac{F_{i,s}^u}{r_{i,s}^u b_{i,s}^u}$. Then, the jitter constraint for TCS^u slices can be expressed as

$$T_{i,s}^u - \mathbb{E}\{T_{i,s}^u\} \leq J_{\max}^u, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_s^u, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^u, \quad (5)$$

where J_{\max}^u is the maximum jitter requirement of the TCS^u slices.

B. TCS^m Slices

For TCS^m slices, we consider the multiple multicast groups transmission mode, where each slice serves multiple groups of terminals with the same demands [19]. The terminals on the TCS^m slice s are divided into several multicast groups which are denoted by $\mathcal{G}_s^m = \{1, \dots, G_s^m\}$, and the set of terminals in group $g \in \mathcal{G}_s^m$ is $\mathcal{I}_{g,s}^m = \{1, \dots, I_{g,s}^m\}$. Let $\mathcal{I}_{1,s}^m \cup \mathcal{I}_{2,s}^m \cup \dots \cup \mathcal{I}_{G_s^m,s}^m = \mathcal{I}_s^m$. The number of groups on the TCS^m slices is equal to the number of terminals on the TCS^u slices, that is $\sum_{s=1}^{S^m} G_s^m = \sum_{s=1}^{S^u} I_s^u$. The total bandwidth of TCS^m slice s is given by $b_s^m = \sum_{g=1}^{G_s^m} b_{g,s}^m$, where $b_{g,s}^m$ is the bandwidth resource occupied by the multicast group g .

The SE $r_{i,g,s}^m$ of the terminal i in group $g \in \mathcal{G}_s^m$ is similar to (3), which is

$$r_{i,g,s}^m = \log(1 + \gamma_i^d) - \sqrt{\frac{C_i^d}{n_i}} Q^{-1}(\vartheta) \log e, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_{g,s}^m, \quad (6)$$

where $C_i^d = 1 - \frac{1}{(1 + \gamma_i^d)^2}$. The SE $r_{g,s}^m$ of group g on the TCS slice s is given by

$$r_{g,s}^m \leq \min_{i \in \mathcal{I}_{g,s}^m} \{r_{i,g,s}^m\}, \forall g \in \mathcal{G}_s^m. \quad (7)$$

In (7), a multicast group must satisfy all terminals under the group to transmit data successfully, thus, the achievable SE $r_{g,s}^m$ is decided by the terminal with the worst channel condition in group g . To meet the QoS requirement D_s^m for all groups under the TCS^m slice s , the delay constraint is

$$\max_{g \in \mathcal{G}_s^m} \left\{ \frac{F_{g,s}^m}{r_{g,s}^m b_{g,s}^m} \right\} \leq D_s^m, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^m, \quad (8)$$

where $F_{g,s}^m$ is the packet length of group g on the TCS^m slice s . We denote the latency of group g on the slice s as $T_{g,s}^m = \frac{F_{g,s}^m}{r_{g,s}^m b_{g,s}^m}$. Similar to (5), the jitter constraint for TCS^m slices is shown as

$$T_{g,s}^m - \mathbb{E}\{T_{g,s}^m\} \leq J_{\max}^m, \forall g \in \mathcal{G}_s^m, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^m, \quad (9)$$

where J_{\max}^m is the maximum jitter requirement of the TCS^m slices.

C. PIS Slices

For PIS slices, the single multicast group transmission mode is used, which is distinct from the TCS^m slices. Each PIS slice only has a multicast group of terminals with the same QoS requirement. We assume that the bandwidth resource occupied

Fig. 2: The transmission process for TSS terminals with two stages.

by the PIS slice s is b_s^p . The SE of terminal i on the PIS slice s can be expressed as

$$r_{i,s}^p = \log(1 + \gamma_i^d), \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_s^p. \quad (10)$$

Then, the achievable SE of multicast PIS slice s is shown as

$$r_s^p \leq \min_{i \in \mathcal{I}_s^p} \{r_{i,s}^p\}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^p. \quad (11)$$

In (11), we also notice that the SE of a multicast slice is decided by the weakest terminal on the slice, which is similar to (7). To meet the QoS requirement of PIS slice s , the throughput constraint is given by

$$r_s^p b_s^p \geq A_s^p, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^p. \quad (12)$$

D. TSS Slices

We utilize the NOMA scheme to enhance the TSS terminals connection capability. The terminals on the TSS slices are classified into multiple sets and the same frequency resource block is shared among the different TSS terminals, forming a *NOMA cluster*.

As shown in Fig. 2, we propose the transmission process for TSS terminals with two stages: random access (RA) control stage and data transmission stage. In the RA control stage, access schemes such as the access class barring (ACB) scheme and the non-limited scheme are chosen for terminals. In the data transmission stage, TSS terminals are allocated to multiple slices. Furthermore, terminals on TSS slice s can be further divided into several NOMA clusters, denoted by a set $\mathcal{J}_s^o = \{1, \dots, J_s^o\}$. The bandwidth of the TSS slice s is given by $b_s^o = \sum_{j=1}^{J_s^o} b_{j,s}^o$, where $b_{j,s}^o$ is the bandwidth of cluster j on TSS slice s .

1) **RA Control:** Massive TSS terminals frequently attempt network access, often leading to significant congestion due to simultaneous mass data transmission [38]. This unexpected congestion can reduce the success probability of RA, cause packet blocking in buffers, and degrade overall system performance. Access control has been recognized as an efficient approach to restrict the access requests of terminals and alleviate congestion [39]. Various access control mechanisms, such as back-off and access class barring (ACB) schemes, have been studied [40]. Given the advantages of the ACB scheme

when transmission resources are limited, we adopt it for TSS terminals in this paper.

- **ACB scheme.** Each TSS terminal generates a random parameter $\theta_i \in [0, 1]$, and initiates an access attempt only when $\theta_i < P_{ACB}$. The value of P_{ACB} is the ACB factor determined by the BS taking into account the resource congestion condition of the TSS slices. By adjusting the suitable ACB factor, the BS can effectively manage and control the access attempts of terminals and ensure the QoS requirements of TSS.

We assume $P_{limited}$ represents the access limited factor under different access control schemes. For the ACB scheme, we set $P_{limited} = P_{ACB}$. Conversely, when no restrictions are applied, the access limited factor is $P_{nolimited} = 1$ [30]. Moreover, we consider the unlimited scheme as the baseline for comparison. It is noteworthy that the successful access of TSS terminal i is shown as an indication of its active status. The terminal i is in the active state to transmit data only when $\theta_i < P_{ACB}$.

2) **Data Transmission based on NOMA clusters:** After the terminals have successfully accessed the WLTCN, they are allocated to TSS slices based on the distinct QoS requirements, and further assigned to multiple NOMA clusters based on an optimal allocation strategy. For the terminal i on the TSS slice s , we define the cluster variable $c_{i,j,s}^o$ as follows

$$c_{i,j,s}^o = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \theta_i < P_{ACB} \text{ and the terminal } i \text{ belongs to} \\ & \text{NOMA cluster } j, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Then, the set of active terminals transmitting data within the NOMA cluster j is represented as $\mathcal{I}_{j,s}^o = \{1, \dots, I_{j,s}^o\}$, where $I_{j,s}^o$ denotes the number of terminals in the cluster j of slice s , and $I_{j,s}^o = \sum_{i=1}^{I_s^o} c_{i,j,s}^o$. We denote the set of cluster variables for TSS terminals on the slice s as \mathcal{C}_s^o , where $c_{i,j,s}^o \in \mathcal{C}_s^o, \forall i, j$. Additionally, it is required that each NOMA cluster cannot be an empty set, which can be expressed as

$$1 \leq \sum_{i=1}^{I_s^o} c_{i,j,s}^o \leq U_{\max}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_s^o, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^o, \quad (14)$$

where U_{\max} is the maximum bound of the number of terminals each NOMA cluster can accommodate. Exploiting the NOMA scheme, the BS receives the superposed signal of the cluster j , and implements SIC technology to decode the signals of all terminals sequentially. The received signal $y_{j,s}^o$ from the cluster j on the TSS slice s at the BS is given by

$$y_{j,s}^o = \sum_{i=1}^{I_{j,s}^o} \sqrt{P_i^u} \mathbf{h}_i^u \mathbf{x}_i^u + \mathbf{n}_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_{j,s}^o, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_s^o. \quad (15)$$

We assume that the channel gains of the terminals have the following rules: $|\mathbf{h}_1^u \mathbf{x}_1^u|^2 \leq |\mathbf{h}_2^u \mathbf{x}_2^u|^2 \leq \dots \leq |\mathbf{h}_{I_{j,s}^o}^u \mathbf{x}_{I_{j,s}^o}^u|^2$. The decoding order at the BS is the opposite of the channel gains. Taking into account the interference from other terminals within the same cluster j , the SINR of terminal i can be

expressed as

$$\gamma_{i,j,s}^o = \frac{c_{i,j,s}^o P_i^t |\mathbf{h}_i^u \mathbf{x}_i^u|^2}{\sum_{k=1}^{i-1} c_{k,j,s}^o P_k^t |\mathbf{h}_k^u \mathbf{x}_k^u|^2 + \sigma^2}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_{j,s}^o. \quad (16)$$

The SE $r_{i,j,s}^o$ of the terminal i in the cluster j is

$$r_{i,j,s}^o = \log(1 + \gamma_{i,j,s}^o), \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_{j,s}^o. \quad (17)$$

To satisfy the QoS requirement R_s^o of the TSS slice s and decode the signals from all TSS terminals successfully, the transmission rate constraint is proposed, which is shown as

$$\min_{i \in \mathcal{I}_{j,s}^o} \{r_{i,j,s}^o\} b_{j,s}^o \geq R_s^o, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_s^o, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^o, \quad (18)$$

where $b_{j,s}^o$ is not only the bandwidth resource of the cluster j , but also the common bandwidth resource each terminal on the cluster j that can be utilized.

Therefore, by adjusting the factor P_{ACB} with the resource congestion state, the access control scheme can be designed to control the number of terminals accessing the TSS slices. Additionally, by satisfying the transmission rate constraint of the TSS slices, we can ensure that the TSS terminals accessing the slices can transmit data reliably. With the above two aspects, we can effectively provide TSS and fulfill the QoS requirements of TSS in WLTCN.

V. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The WLTCN is a private network, and there has been no licensed spectrum for WLTCN. The spectrum is obtained by leasing it from telecommunication operators. Saving bandwidth resource can reduce the train operating costs and carry more smart services within WLTCN in the future. Thus, we formulate the slicing strategy in WLTCN as the system bandwidth minimization problem including slicing resource allocation for TCS, PIS, and TSS and non-orthogonal access grouping for TSS terminals, which can satisfy the different QoS requirements of the above services.

We denote the bandwidth resource allocated to all slices as $\mathcal{F} = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}^u} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_s^u} b_{i,s}^u + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}^m} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}_s^m} b_{g,s}^m + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}^p} b_s^p + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}^o} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_s^o} b_{j,s}^o$. For convenience, we define the parameter vectors $\mathbf{b}^u = \{b_{i,s}^u\}$, $\mathbf{b}^m = \{b_{g,s}^m\}$, $\mathbf{b}^p = \{b_s^p\}$, $\mathbf{b}^o = \{b_{j,s}^o\}$, $\mathcal{C} = \{\mathcal{C}_s^o\}$. The system bandwidth minimization problem is formulated as follows

$$(P_0) \quad \min_{\mathbf{b}^u, \mathbf{b}^m, \mathbf{b}^p, \mathbf{b}^o, \mathcal{C}} \quad \mathcal{F} \quad (19)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad (4), (5), (7), (8), (9), (11), (12), \\ (14), \text{ and } (18),$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{\mathcal{J}_s^o} c_{i,j,s}^o \in \{1, 0\}, \\ \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_{j,s}^o, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_s^o, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^o, \quad (19a)$$

$$b_{j,s}^o \geq b_{\min}^o, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_s^o, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^o. \quad (19b)$$

For TCS^u and TCS^m slices, constraints (4), (7) and (8) denote the latency constraints. Constraints (5) and (9) denote the low-jitter constraints. Constraints (11) and (12) meet the throughput requirements of PIS slices. Constraint (14) denotes a range for the number of TSS terminals that can be carried

in a NOMA cluster. Constraint (18) denotes the transmission rate requirements of TSS slices and ensures all TSS terminals can be decoded successfully. Constraint (19a) guarantees that each terminal is allocated to one NOMA cluster at most. Constraint (19b) indicates that the bandwidth of each cluster has a minimum bound b_{\min}^o to prevent the bandwidth value assigned to a cluster from being too small to be divided. In this paper, considering the bandwidth of one subchannel is 15 KHz, we set the minimum bandwidth bound $b_{\min}^o = 15$ KHz for the simulation results of Section VII.

The challenges of the problem (P_0) are listed as follows. Firstly, the optimal problem is non-convex due to the presence of expectations in constraints (5) and (9), making it difficult to solve directly. In addition, the binary variable $c_{i,j,s}^o$ makes the problem (P_0) become a mixed-integer non-linear programming (MINLP) problem, which is known to be NP-hard and poses significant challenges to solve.

VI. THE OPTIMAL SLICING STRATEGY

In this section, we transform and decompose the original bandwidth minimization problem (P_0) into two subproblems. A joint bandwidth optimization and terminal clustering (JBOTC) algorithm is proposed to obtain the optimal slicing strategy for TCS, PIS, and TSS. Additionally, the closed-form expressions of the optimal bandwidth allocation for the above services are investigated. Finally, we analyze the complexity of the proposed JBOTC algorithm.

A. Problem Transformation

Based on the challenges mentioned above in the Section V, we first tackle the $\mathbb{E}\{T_{i,s}^u\}$ and $\mathbb{E}\{T_{g,s}^m\}$ in constraints (5) and (9). For the TCS^m slices, relying on the block-fading channel characteristic, we assume that the expectation of bandwidth allocated to a TCS^m group is a constant. The package length $F_{g,s}^m$ is fixed. Thus, we rewrite the $\mathbb{E}\{T_{g,s}^m\}$ in constraint (9) as

$$\mathbb{E}\{T_{g,s}^m\} = \mathbb{E}\left\{\frac{F_{g,s}^m}{r_{g,s}^m b_{g,s}^m}\right\} \approx \frac{F_{g,s}^m}{b_{g,s}^m} \mathbb{E}\left\{\frac{1}{r_{g,s}^m}\right\} \\ \stackrel{(a)}{=} \frac{F_{g,s}^m}{b_{g,s}^m} \mathbb{E}\left\{\frac{1}{f(\gamma)}\right\} = \frac{F_{g,s}^m}{b_{g,s}^m} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{f(\gamma)} p_{\gamma}(\gamma) d\gamma, \quad (20)$$

where step (a) is achieved by using $r_{g,s}^m = f(\gamma)$, and γ denotes the instantaneous SNR per bit of group g on the TCS slice s . $p_{\gamma}(\gamma)$ denotes the probability density function (PDF) of γ [41]. The same application is for the variable $\mathbb{E}\{T_{i,s}^u\}$. We denote the auxiliary variables as $A_{i,s}^u = \mathbb{E}\{\frac{1}{r_{i,s}^u}\}$ and $A_{g,s}^m = \mathbb{E}\{\frac{1}{r_{g,s}^m}\}$.

After simplifying the jitter constraints of TCS^u and TCS^m slices, we substitute constraints (4) and (8) into constraints (5) and (9), respectively. The desired results are as follows

$$\frac{F_{i,s}^u}{b_{i,s}^u} \leq \min\left\{D_s^u r_{i,s}^u, \frac{J_{\max}^u}{\frac{1}{r_{i,s}^u} - A_{i,s}^u}\right\}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_s^u, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^u. \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{F_{g,s}^m}{b_{g,s}^m} \leq \min\left\{D_s^m r_{g,s}^m, \frac{J_{\max}^m}{\frac{1}{r_{g,s}^m} - A_{g,s}^m}\right\}, \forall g \in \mathcal{G}_s^m, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^m. \quad (22)$$

Similarly, by simplifying the constraints (18) and (19b) of TSS slices, we can derive the following inequality

$$\frac{R_s^o}{b_{j,s}^o} \leq \min \left\{ \min_{i \in \mathcal{I}_{j,s}^o} \{r_{i,j,s}^o\}, \frac{R_s^o}{b_{\min}^o} \right\}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_s^o, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^o. \quad (23)$$

Lemma 1. During the problem solving, the constraints (12), (21), (22) and (23) are active inequality constraints. Then, we can derive that an optimal solution $\{\mathbf{b}^u, \mathbf{b}^m, \mathbf{b}^p, \mathbf{b}^o, \mathcal{C}\}$ to problem (P_0) always satisfies

$$\begin{cases} \frac{F_{i,s}^u}{b_{i,s}^u} = \min \left\{ D_s^u r_{i,s}^u, \frac{J_{\max}^u}{\frac{1}{r_{i,s}^u} - A_{i,s}^u} \right\}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_s^u, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^u, \\ \frac{F_{g,s}^m}{b_{g,s}^m} = \min \left\{ D_s^m r_{g,s}^m, \frac{J_{\max}^m}{\frac{1}{r_{g,s}^m} - A_{g,s}^m} \right\}, \forall g \in \mathcal{G}_s^m, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^m, \\ r_s^p b_s^p = A_s^p, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^p, \\ \frac{R_s^o}{b_{j,s}^o} = \min \left\{ \min_{i \in \mathcal{I}_{j,s}^o} \{r_{i,j,s}^o\}, \frac{R_s^o}{b_{\min}^o} \right\}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_s^o, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^o. \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

Proof. Please refer to the Appendix A. \square

Then, the problem (P_0) can be transformed equivalently as

$$(P_1) \quad \min_{\mathbf{b}^u, \mathbf{b}^m, \mathbf{b}^p, \mathbf{b}^o, \mathcal{C}} \mathcal{F} \quad (25)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \frac{F_{i,s}^u}{b_{i,s}^u} = \min \left\{ D_s^u r_{i,s}^u, \frac{J_{\max}^u}{\frac{1}{r_{i,s}^u} - A_{i,s}^u} \right\}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_s^u, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^u, \quad (25a)$$

$$\frac{F_{g,s}^m}{\min \{b_{g,s}^m D_s^m, b_{g,s}^m J_{\max}^m + F_{g,s}^m A_{g,s}^m\}} \leq r_{i,g,s}^m, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_{g,s}^m, \forall g \in \mathcal{G}_s^m, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^m, \quad (25b)$$

$$\frac{A_s^p}{b_s^p} \leq r_{i,s}^p, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_s^p, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^p, \quad (25c)$$

$$\frac{R_s^o}{b_{j,s}^o} = \min \left\{ \min_{i \in \mathcal{I}_{j,s}^o} \{r_{i,j,s}^o\}, \frac{R_s^o}{b_{\min}^o} \right\}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_{j,s}^o, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_s^o, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^o, \quad (25d)$$

$$(14), \text{ and } (19a).$$

We can observe that the transformed problem (P_1) is still difficult to solve due to the existence of binary variable $c_{i,j,s}^o$. Hence, we decouple the bandwidth allocation variables $\{\mathbf{b}^u, \mathbf{b}^m, \mathbf{b}^p, \mathbf{b}^o\}$ and the TSS terminal grouping variable \mathcal{C} .

B. Optimal Bandwidth Resource Allocation

Based on the Lemma 1, we can derive the deterministic closed-form bandwidth expression $b_{i,s}^u$ of TCS^u slice s and $b_{j,s}^o$ of TSS slice s from the problem (P_1) which do not need to be optimized iteratively with algorithm due to unicast characteristics. The closed-form bandwidth expressions are shown as

$$b_{i,s}^u = \frac{F_{i,s}^u}{\min \left\{ D_s^u r_{i,s}^u, \frac{J_{\max}^u}{\frac{1}{r_{i,s}^u} - A_{i,s}^u} \right\}}, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_s^u, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^u, \quad (26)$$

$$b_{j,s}^o = \frac{R_s^o}{\min \left\{ \min_{i \in \mathcal{I}_{j,s}^o} \{r_{i,j,s}^o\}, \frac{R_s^o}{b_{\min}^o} \right\}}, \forall j \in \mathcal{J}_s^o, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^o. \quad (27)$$

Based on these expressions, we assume that the terminal clustering variable \mathcal{C} is given. Thus, we only need to optimize the bandwidth allocation $\{\mathbf{b}^m, \mathbf{b}^p\}$ and obtain the optimal solution based on the iterative optimizations. The slicing bandwidth allocation problem with the given terminal clustering variable \mathcal{C} is

$$(P_{2A}) \quad \min_{\mathbf{b}^m, \mathbf{b}^p} \mathcal{F} \quad (28)$$

s.t. (25b), and (25c).

Due to the convexity of the problem (P_{2A}) , the dual decomposition method [42], [43] is used to solve the bandwidth allocation problem.

The Lagrangian function of problem (P_{2A}) can be given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{b}^p, \mathbf{b}^m, \boldsymbol{\lambda}, \mathbf{v}) = & \mathcal{F} + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}^p} \lambda_s \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_s^p} \left(\frac{A_s^p}{b_s^p} - r_{i,s}^p \right) \\ & + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}^m} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}_s^m} v_{g,s} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_{g,s}^m} y(b_{g,s}^m), \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

where $y(b_{g,s}^m) = \frac{F_{g,s}^m}{\min \{b_{g,s}^m D_s^m, b_{g,s}^m J_{\max}^m + F_{g,s}^m A_{g,s}^m\}} - r_{i,g,s}^m$, $\boldsymbol{\lambda} = \{\lambda_s\}$, $\mathbf{v} = \{v_{g,s}\}$. Then, we solve the original problem by dual optimization to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & (\mathbf{b}^{p,*}, \mathbf{b}^{m,*}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*, \mathbf{v}^*) \\ & = \arg \left\{ \max_{\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \mathbf{v} \geq 0} \min_{\mathbf{b}^p, \mathbf{b}^m} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{b}^p, \mathbf{b}^m, \boldsymbol{\lambda}, \mathbf{v}) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Then, the inner minimization in (30), i.e., dual function of problem (P_{2A}) , can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} g(\boldsymbol{\lambda}^*, \mathbf{v}^*) & \triangleq \min_{\mathbf{b}^p, \mathbf{b}^m} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{b}^p, \mathbf{b}^m, \boldsymbol{\lambda}, \mathbf{v}) \\ & = \min_{\mathbf{b}^p, \mathbf{b}^m} \left(\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}^p} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_s^p} g_{i,s}^p(b_s^p) + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}^m} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}_s^m} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}_{g,s}^m} g_{i,g,s}^m(b_{g,s}^m) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where $g_{i,s}^p(b_s^p) = \frac{b_s^p}{I_s^p} + \lambda_s \left(\frac{A_s^p}{b_s^p} - r_{i,s}^p \right)$, and $g_{i,g,s}^m(b_{g,s}^m) = \frac{b_{g,s}^m}{I_{g,s}^m} + \frac{v_{g,s} F_{g,s}^m}{\min \{b_{g,s}^m D_s^m, J_{\max}^m b_{g,s}^m + F_{g,s}^m A_{g,s}^m\}} - r_{i,g,s}^m$. Then, we can solve the dual subproblem $g_{i,s}^p(b_s^p)$ and $g_{i,g,s}^m(b_{g,s}^m)$ according to the first-order optimization condition with a distributed fashion. The closed-form expressions of the optimal bandwidth allocation are obtained. The optimal bandwidth allocation of TCS^m slice $s \in \mathcal{S}^m$ can be expressed as

$$b_{g,s}^{m,*} = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{v_{g,s}^* F_{g,s}^m J_{\max}^m}{J_{\max}^m} - \frac{F_{g,s}^m A_{g,s}^m}{J_{\max}^m}}, & n_1 \geq n_2, \\ \sqrt{\frac{v_{g,s}^* F_{g,s}^m J_{\max}^m}{D_s^m}}, & n_1 \leq n_2, \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

where $n_1 = D_s^m r_{g,s}^m$, $n_2 = \frac{J_{\max}^m}{\frac{1}{r_{g,s}^m} - A_{g,s}^m}$. The optimal bandwidth allocation of PIS slice $s \in \mathcal{S}^p$ can be written as

$$b_s^{p,*} = \sqrt{\lambda_s^* A_s^p I_s^p}. \quad (33)$$

The details of the dual-decomposition-based bandwidth allocation (DBA) algorithm are illustrated in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Dual-decomposition-based Bandwidth Allocation (DBA) Algorithm

Require: Initial value $\lambda_s^{(0)}, v_{g,s}^{(0)}$, tolerance $\Delta = 10^{-3}$.

Ensure: Optimal bandwidth allocation $\{\mathbf{b}^p, \mathbf{b}^m\}$.

- 1: Derive the value $A_{g,s}^m$ for each group in TCS^m slices.
 - 2: Define the packet length F_s^m for each group in TCS^m slices.
 - 3: **while** $|\mathcal{F}^{(k)} - \mathcal{F}^{(k-1)}| \leq \Delta$ **do**
 - 4: Update $b_s^{p,(k)}, b_{g,s}^{m,(k)}$ by calculating (33) and (32).
 - 5: Update $\lambda_s^{(k)} \leftarrow \left[\lambda_s^{(k-1)} + \text{step}^{(k-1)} \nabla g \left(\lambda_s^{(k-1)} \right) \right]^+$.
 - 6: Update $v_{g,s}^{(k)}$ in the same way as $\lambda_s^{(k)}$.
 - 7: Update $k \leftarrow k + 1$.
 - 8: **end while**
-

C. Optimal TSS Terminal Grouping Strategy

After solving the problem (P_{2A}) at n^{th} iteration, we obtain the optimal bandwidth allocation strategy $\{\mathbf{b}^m, \mathbf{b}^p\}$ of TCS^m and PIS slices. The optimal bandwidth $\{\mathbf{b}^u, \mathbf{b}^o\}$ of TCS^u and TSS slices can also be derived from the deterministic closed-form expressions (26) and (27). Given the closed-form expressions of bandwidth variables $\{\mathbf{b}^u, \mathbf{b}^m, \mathbf{b}^p, \mathbf{b}^o\}$, we propose a joint bandwidth optimization and terminal clustering (JBOTC) algorithm to obtain the optimal slicing resource allocation for TCS, PIS, and TSS and terminal grouping strategy for TSS. The part of terminal clustering problem with optimal variable \mathcal{C} can be formulated as follows

$$(P_{2B}) \quad \min_{\mathcal{C}} \quad \mathcal{F} \quad (34)$$

s.t. (14), and (19a).

We can notice that the exhaustive method can obtain the optimal terminal grouping strategy \mathcal{C}_s^o . However, the complexity is extremely high if the maximum bound U_{\max} is large for the number of terminals in a NOMA cluster. In practical implementation, one approach to reducing the complexity of SIC technology is by limiting the number of terminals in a cluster by setting a small value for U_{\max} . For instance, in some studies [44]–[46], two terminals are grouped and multiple terminal groups are formed, enabling various non-orthogonal multiple access schemes with acceptable SIC decoding complexity.

Hence, in this paper, we consider that U_{\max} is 2, i.e., each NOMA cluster can accommodate a maximum of two TSS terminals. However, with the $U_{\max} = 2$, the complexity of the exhaustive method is also as high as $\mathcal{O}((N-1)!!)$, where N represents the number of TSS terminals needed to be grouped and $(\cdot)!!$ denotes the double factorial. Moreover, considering the enormous number of TSS terminals in WLTCN, we propose a low-complexity algorithm to derive the optimal TSS terminal grouping strategy instead of the exhaustive scheme. The detailed description of the problem is as follows.

We divide the TSS terminals into multiple clusters. Terminals in the same cluster share bandwidth resource by NOMA scheme. Considering that the cluster j has two terminal a and b , we define $\xi_{a,b}$ as the difference in bandwidth consumption of cluster j between NOMA and OMA scheme. A higher $\xi_{a,b}$

Algorithm 2 Joint Bandwidth Optimization and Terminal Clustering (JBOTC) Algorithm

Require: Initial value $\mathcal{C}_s^{o(0)}, \lambda_s^{(0)}, v_{g,s}^{(0)}$, tolerance $\Delta = 10^{-3}$.

Ensure: Optimal slicing strategy $\{\mathbf{b}^u, \mathbf{b}^m, \mathbf{b}^p, \mathbf{b}^o, \mathcal{C}\}$ and optimal objective bandwidth \mathcal{F} .

- 1: **repeat**
 - 2: Derive the value $A_{i,s}^u$ for each terminal in TCS^u slices.
 - 3: Define the packet length $F_{i,s}^u$ for each terminal in TCS^u slices.
 - 4: Derive $b_{i,s}^u$ by calculating (26).
 - 5: /*Algorithm 1: DBA Algorithm*/
 - 6: Define the set of TSS terminals $\psi \leftarrow \mathcal{I}_s^o$.
 - 7: Define the value $\xi_{a,b}$ for any terminal a, b .
 - 8: Define $\hat{j} \leftarrow 1$.
 - 9: **while** $\xi_{a,b} > 0, \forall a, b$ **do**
 - 10: Select optimal $\xi_{a,b}$ and group the terminals a and b .
 - 11: Update the set of terminals $\psi \leftarrow \psi \setminus \{a, b\}$.
 - 12: Update the $\mathcal{C}_s^{o(k)} : c_{a,\hat{j},s}^o \leftarrow 1, c_{b,\hat{j},s}^o \leftarrow 1$.
 - 13: Update $\hat{j} \leftarrow \hat{j} + 1$.
 - 14: **end while**
 - 15: **if** $\psi \neq \emptyset$ **then**
 - 16: **for all** terminal $a \in \psi$ **do**
 - 17: Update the $\mathcal{C}_s^{o(k)} : c_{a,\hat{j},s}^o \leftarrow 1$.
 - 18: Update $\hat{j} \leftarrow \hat{j} + 1$.
 - 19: **end for**
 - 20: **end if**
 - 21: Derive $b_{j,s}^{o,(k)}$ by calculating (27).
 - 22: Update $k \leftarrow k + 1$.
 - 23: **until** $|\mathcal{F}^{(k)} - \mathcal{F}^{(k-1)}| \leq \Delta$
 - 24: **return** $\mathcal{F}^{(k)}$
-

indicates more bandwidth gain value achieved by grouping terminals a and b with NOMA scheme. Specifically, we choose and group terminals one by one until two conditions are met: (1) all terminals have been grouped, and (2) the objective value of problem (P_{2B}) no longer decreases. During iterations, the system evaluates the value $\xi_{a,b}$ of any two terminal a and b and selects the cluster that is most advantageous to the objective function. Then, the system updates the set \mathcal{C}_s^o for TSS slice $s \in \mathcal{S}^o$ and continues to group the remaining terminals. If some terminals cannot find suitable other terminals to form a cluster, they will access slices orthogonally instead of the NOMA scheme to minimize bandwidth consumption. Thus, the proposed JBOTC algorithm effectively solves the 0-1 terminal clustering problem. Based on the above analysis, the details of the JBOTC algorithm are shown in Algorithm 2.

D. Algorithm Complexity Analysis

In this subsection, we analyze the computational complexity of the proposed JBOTC algorithm in the bandwidth allocation and terminal clustering strategy. We set the number of iterations as K_1 at Algorithm 2. The optimal bandwidth allocation $\{\mathbf{b}^m, \mathbf{b}^p\}$ can be derived from the Algorithm 1. In particular, lines 6-20 of Algorithm 2 describe the TSS terminal grouping scheme. Considering that the number of TSS terminals is N ,

the computational complexity of the loop is $\mathcal{O}(N)$. Therefore, the computation complexity of the Algorithm 2 is $\mathcal{O}(NK_1)$. By comparing with the exhaustive searching algorithm, we observe that the JBOTC algorithm significantly reduces the complexity while achieving better performance than the other baseline schemes, which are demonstrated in the simulation results in Section VII.

VII. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this paper, we propose a JBOTC algorithm to tackle the challenge of services co-existence and bandwidth resource allocation for TCS, PIS, and TSS in WLTCN. Extensive simulations have been conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed slicing strategy, such as the impact on bandwidth allocation caused by the SNR, the number of terminals, and the QoS requirements within WLTCN. The simulation results illustrate the performance superiority for saving bandwidth of the JBOTC algorithm to the benchmark schemes.

A. Simulation Settings

We consider one carriage scenario of WLTCN, in which there is one BS with $K = 4$ antennas and several terminals each equipped with a single antenna. The BS and terminals are on a rectangular carriage with an area of 25×3 (m^2). The distances between BS and terminals in different slices are random and independent. We suppose that the channel model is Rayleigh block-fading model and the power received of a terminal d m from RRU is $PL(dB) = 32.4 + 20 \log_{10}(f_c) + 31.9 \log_{10}(d)$, where $f_c = 3.5$ GHz denotes the center frequency. The transmission power of BS and terminal are $P_i^{BS} = 0.5$ W and $P_i^t = 0.2$ W, respectively. The noise power $\sigma^2 = -70$ dBm. For the finite block-length regime, we assume the finite block-length $n_i = 200$, and the transmission error probability $\vartheta = 10^{-5}$. Furthermore, we suppose that the packet length $F_{i,s}^u$ and $F_{g,s}^m$ of TCS terminals follow the uniform distribution with $[450, 500]$ bytes. The jitter parameters J_{max}^u and J_{max}^m are 1 ms. Unless otherwise specified, the access limited factor $P_{limited} = P_{ACB} = 0.9$. The minimum bandwidth bound of NOMA cluster is $b_{min}^o = 15$ KHz. Then, we set the number of multicast groups on the TCS^m slices and the number of unicast terminals on the TCS^u slices to be equal, given by $\sum_{s=1}^{S^m} G_s^m = \sum_{s=1}^{S^u} I_s^u = 4$.

B. Single Slice Results

To effectively demonstrate the performance of the proposed models and algorithm, we initially focus on analyzing the results for a single type of slice.

To begin with, we show the impact of channel quality differences on the bandwidth consumption of the TCS^m and PIS slices to investigate the characteristics of multicast slices, respectively. There are two kinds of multicast slices in WLTCN. From constraints (7) and (11), we can see that a multicast group must guarantee the transmission of all terminals under the group. Then, we use the variance of SNR (Var-SNR) to characterize channel quality variations of all terminals in a multicast group. We set a slice under each

Fig. 3: Impact of the channel differences of terminals on multicast slices bandwidth consumption, i.e., (a) TCS^m slice (b) PIS slice.

Fig. 4: Impact of the number of terminals on TSS bandwidth consumption with different QoS requirements.

type of multicast slice to carry the terminals, the TCS^m slice is $\{12, 15\text{ms}\}$, the PIS slice is $\{12, 6\text{Mb/s}\}$. Each slice is denoted by an array containing two attributes, i.e., the number of terminals and the QoS requirements.

The influence of channel variations of terminals on bandwidth consumption for TCS^m and PIS slices can be observed in Fig. 3. We can derive that the TCS^m and PIS slices require more bandwidth as the Var-SNR increases. Additionally, the fluctuation range of bandwidth consumption also expands with higher Var-SNR value. Since the large Var-SNR means a higher probability of the terminals with poor channel conditions on a multicast group, the SE of the multicast group is determined by the terminal with the worst channel condition on the group. While there are wide variations of channel qualities of terminals on a multicast group, more bandwidth should be reserved. Consequently, for TCS^m slices with real-time transmission demands, it is possible to reserve a specific amount of bandwidth by investigating the channel differences among TCS^m terminals, which satisfies the strict QoS requirements of TCS.

To establish a benchmark for comparison, we consider the following baseline cases:

Fig. 5: Impact of the TSS terminals access ability on bandwidth consumption.

Fig. 7: The relationship between the system bandwidth consumption and SNR.

Fig. 6: The relationship between the bandwidth consumption of each slice and SNR.

Fig. 8: Impact of the different slices combinations on the system bandwidth.

- Full orthogonal access scheme (OMA): All terminals access the slices by the orthogonal scheme for TCS, PIS, and TSS.
- Greedy search and access scheme (GRE): Terminals of TCS and PIS are employed with OMA. TSS terminals access with NOMA and use the greedy search algorithm to derive the optimal terminal grouping strategy.
- Ant colony search and access scheme (ANT): Terminals of TCS and PIS utilize the OMA scheme for access. TSS terminals access the slices with NOMA and are grouped by the ant colony search algorithm.
- Strong-Weak group and access scheme (SW): TCS and PIS terminals access to the slices with OMA. TSS terminals with strong channel conditions are grouped with those with weak conditions [44].
- Strong-Medium group and access scheme (SM): The OMA scheme is employed by both TCS and PIS terminals for access. Subsequently, we group the TSS terminals with strong channel conditions and those with medium channel conditions [44].

Secondly, in Fig. 4, we analyze the situation that the bandwidth consumption of TSS slices with the number of terminals under different QoS requirements R_s^o . Meanwhile, we compare the performance of the proposed JBOTC algorithm with the OMA scheme. We assume that there is one TSS slice and the

terminal access limited factor is $P_{nolimited} = 1$. From Fig. 4, we can notice that the gap of bandwidth consumption between the JBOTC algorithm and the OMA scheme becomes larger with the increasing number of TSS terminals. Moreover, in terms of minimizing the bandwidth resource, our proposed JBOTC algorithm is superior to the OMA scheme regardless of different QoS requirements.

Fig. 5 illustrates the bandwidth consumption of TSS slices as a function of the access limited factor P_{ACB} of the TSS terminals. The number of terminals on a TSS slice is fixed to $I_s^o = 40$. We present the results under the proposed JBOTC algorithm and other baseline schemes. It is observed that the bandwidth consumption increases gradually with the increase of the factor P_{ACB} of TSS terminals. The reason is that a higher P_{ACB} corresponds to a greater number of terminals successfully connected to the WLTN. More importantly, our proposed algorithm exhibits superior characteristics for the larger value of P_{ACB} , which means that there are more terminals on the slice. The simulation result is consistent with the conclusion from Fig. 4.

C. Multiple Slice Results

In order to further investigate the effectiveness of the proposed JBOTC algorithm in slice bandwidth saving, we can

examine the performance results with the four types of slices in WLTCN, i.e., TCS^u, TCS^m, PIS, and TSS slices.

For the above slices, in Fig. 6, we set that each type of slice has one slice with two attributes: the slice parameter of TCS^m slice is {6, 6ms}, and the TCS^u slice is {2, 6ms}. The PIS slice is {6, 6Mb/s}. The TSS slice is {40, 200kb/s}. The access limited factor P_{ACB} for TSS terminals is 0.9. We analyze the relationship between the bandwidth allocation of each slice and the different SNR in Fig. 6. It is observed that the bandwidth of each slice decreases and gradually stabilizes with the increasing SNR. Then, we compare the whole bandwidth consumption results in WLTCN with different algorithms in Fig. 7. We can conclude that the system bandwidth with all algorithms decreases while the SNR increases, and the proposed JBOTC algorithm outperforms the benchmark schemes GRE, SM, and OMA. More importantly, as the SNR increases, the JBOTC scheme also performs closely to the OMA scheme since the system does not need to divide terminals into multiple NOMA clusters to transmit data if the channel characteristic of each terminal is good enough.

In Fig. 8, we compare the system bandwidth consumption with distinct slices combinations (from C1 to C6). The parameters for TCS^u, TCS^m, PIS, and TSS slices under the slices combinations C1 to C6 are shown in Table I. For clarity, every type of service has one slice, and the delay constraints of both TCS^u and TCS^m slices are identical. The average SNR of terminals is 10 dB. We can observe that the higher throughput requirement of PIS slice leads to more bandwidth consumption (from C1 to C2). From C2 to C3, it is worth noting that there is little impact on the system bandwidth consumption with the increasing number of terminals in multicast slices, such as TCS^m and PIS slices. The reason is that the Var-SNR among terminals holds steady, resulting in no significant change in bandwidth consumption. This conclusion is consistent with Fig. 3 which describes the relationship between bandwidth and channel quality differences of multicast terminals. From C2 to C4, the result shows that as the delay requirements D_s^u and D_s^m are tightened from 15 ms to 10 ms, there is no significant change in the system bandwidth consumption. The reason is that both delay requirements with 15 ms and 10 ms are too loose to impose a constraint. In this case, the jitter constraint $J_{max} = 1$ ms remains effective. However, the system bandwidth increases significantly (from C4 to C5) while the delay requirement becomes more stringent. Besides, it can be observed that the bandwidth consumption increases with the increase of QoS requirement of TSS (from C5 to C6). We can also see that the JBOTC algorithm consistently realizes smaller system bandwidth consumption compared to the baseline schemes.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper illustrates a RAN slicing architecture within WLTCN to realize the multiple services co-existence, including TCS, PIS, and TSS. Due to the heterogeneous characteristics and QoS requirements of the above services within WLTCN, we propose a JBOTC algorithm to efficiently allocate slicing bandwidth for TCS, PIS, and TSS to guarantee the

TABLE I: THE SLICE PARAMETERS

Seq	TCS ^u	TCS ^m	PIS	TSS
C1	{2, 15ms}	{6, 15ms}	{6, 4Mb/s}	{40, 200kb/s}
C2	{2, 15ms}	{6, 15ms}	{6, 6Mb/s}	{40, 200kb/s}
C3	{2, 15ms}	{12, 15ms}	{12, 6Mb/s}	{40, 200kb/s}
C4	{2, 10ms}	{6, 10ms}	{6, 6Mb/s}	{40, 200kb/s}
C5	{2, 3ms}	{6, 3ms}	{6, 6Mb/s}	{40, 200kb/s}
C6	{2, 3ms}	{6, 3ms}	{6, 6Mb/s}	{40, 300kb/s}

transmission demands and save bandwidth resource as well, which can reduce train operating costs. Besides, the closed-form expressions of the optimal bandwidth allocation are derived. Simulation results demonstrate that our proposed slicing strategy can provide these different services in WLTCN. In addition, in terms of minimizing slicing bandwidth, our method is superior to the baseline algorithms.

For future work, we will explore slicing strategies and resource allocation in moving networks with train-to-ground links. In addition, the influence of diverse slicing strategies on resource allocation within WLTCN requires further investigation. A key challenge is achieving deterministic service transmission across both onboard and offboard links. This involves addressing issues such as multiple-antenna terminals, imperfect train-to-ground links, and the joint allocation of frequency and computing resources.

APPENDIX A PROOF OF LEMMA 1

We assume that there exists an optimal solution $\{b^u, b^m, b^p, b^o, \mathcal{C}\}$ that can make any of the expressions in the constraint (24) not equal. This indicates that we can continue to reduce the bandwidth allocation $\{b^m, b^u, b^p, b^o\}$ or modify the terminal grouping strategy $\{\mathcal{C}\}$ to converge towards the desired objective [19].

This completes the proof.

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